

Synthesis of 2, 5—Diaryloxazoles

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Some of the 2,5—diaryloxazoles are well known for its scintillation properties. Hippuryl chloride has been used to synthesise benzoylaminomethyl phenyl ketone by the Friedel-Crafts acylation of benzene which on cyclodehydration gave 2,5—diphenyl oxazole. This work has been extended to synthesise other commonly used scintillation solutes. N.M.R. spectra for different compounds has also been studied.

The reaction of hippuryl chloride on benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride reported earlier¹ has been extended to toluene, biphenyl and naphthalene to obtain corresponding benzoylaminomethyl aryl ketones. These ketones on cyclodehydration gave 2,5-diaryloxazoles which are commonly used in scintillation spectrometry^{2,3,4}.

Reaction conditions and yields for the acylation of aromatic hydrocarbons are given in Table 1. In all cases, three moles of aluminium chloride are added to a suspension of one mole each of hippuryl chloride and hydrocarbon in dry solvent as described earlier¹. After decomposition by dilute hydrochloric acid, benzoylaminomethyl aryl ketones are isolated by filtration and washed with ether. In case of toluene, major portion of the product dissolves in the solvent. The product can be recovered by evaporation of carbon disulphide. Naphthalene gives poor yield^{5,6} due to secondary reactions with anhydrous aluminium chloride. Anthracene does not react under these experimental conditions due to its low solubility.

TABLE 1

Reaction conditions for the synthesis of benzoylaminomethyl ketones

Hydrocarbon	Acid chloride	AlCl ₃	Solvent	Temp.	Yield
Moles	Moles	Moles	ml	°C	%
Benzene ¹	0.10	0.30	75	80	60
Toluene	0.20	0.60	200	46	48
Biphenyl	0.15	0.45	300	46	40
Naphthalene	0.15	0.45	450	0-10	25

Benzoylamino ketones are converted into oxazoles by dehydration. Concentrated sulphuric acid does not bring about cyclodehydration in all the cases. However,

phosphorus oxychloride has been found to be suitable for the same. Reaction conditions and yields for cyclodehydration are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Reaction conditions for the synthesis of 2-phenyl-5-aryl oxazoles

Hydrocarbon	Dehydrating agent	Temp (°C)	Time (hrs.)	Yield (%)
Benzene ¹	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	30	1	80
Toluene	POCl ₃	108	5	75
Biphenyl	POCl ₃	108	5	75
Naphthalene	POCl ₃	108	5	70

EXPERIMENTAL

The structure of the various compounds was confirmed by Varian A-60A Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (δ) relative to internal tetramethylsilane standard. Deuteriochloroform was used as a solvent.

Benzoylaminomethyl aryl ketones: These ketones are prepared by slow addition of anhydrous aluminium chloride to a suspension of hippuryl chloride^{11,19} and aromatic hydrocarbon maintained at 0–10°. The solvent is either the hydrocarbon itself or dry carbon disulphide. The reaction mixture was stirred until the evolution of HCl gas ceased and then refluxed on water bath for 4 hrs. After cooling, the mixture was decomposed by slowly pouring it into cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and ether and then dried in air. The characteristics of the various ketones, thus obtained, are given below:

Benzoylaminomethyl phenyl ketone, m.p. 122°–3° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 122°,³ 123°,¹⁴ and 124°.¹⁵ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 4.2 (2H, –CH₂–CO–, doublet, J = 4 cps), 6.4–7.5 (11H, aromatic and –CO–NH–, multiplet).

Benzoylaminomethyl p-tolyl ketone, m.p. 114°–6° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 118°–119°.¹⁷ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 1.6 (3H, –CH₃, singlet), 4.1 (2H, –CH₂–CO–, doublet, J = 4 cps), 6.3–7.3 (10H, aromatic and –CO–NH–, multiplet).

Benzoylaminomethyl 4-biphenyl ketone, m.p. 178°–180° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 182°–186°.⁷ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 4.2 (2H, –CH₂–CO–, doublet, J = 4 cps), 6.4–7.5 (15H, aromatic and –CO–NH–, multiplet).

Benzoylaminomethyl 1-naphthyl ketone, m.p. 146°–7° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 150°.¹⁶ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 4.1 (2H, –CH₂–CO–, doublet, J = 4 cps), 6.5–7.5 (13H, aromatic and –CO–NH–, multiplet).

2-Phenyl-5-aryl oxazoles: These oxazoles were prepared by refluxing the respective ketones, with 4–5 moles of POCl₃ for 5 hrs. After cooling the flask, reaction mixture

was slowly added to a mixture of ice and water with continuous stirring. Solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried in air. The characteristics of various oxazoles, thus obtained, are given below.

2,5-Diphenyl oxazole, m.p. 71°–72° from pet. ether. Lit. m.p. 70°–71°,¹⁵ 73°,¹⁴ 71°–72°,³ and 74°¹³. NMR spectrum gave peaks at 6.4–7.5 (aromatic multiplet).

2-Phenyl-5-p-tolyl-oxazole, m.p. 74° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 81°–82°¹⁷ and 81°.¹⁸ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 1.6 (3H, –CH₃, singlet), 6.5–7.5 (aromatic multiplet).

2-Phenyl-5-(4-biphenyl)-oxazole, m.p. 155° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 158°.⁷ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 6.4–7.5 (aromatic multiplet).

2-Phenyl-5-(1-naphthyl)-oxazole, m.p. 108°–109° from ethanol. Lit. m.p. 116°–117°.¹⁶ NMR spectrum gave peaks at 6.5–7.5 (aromatic multiplet).

All these oxazoles give satisfactory scintillation characteristics.

It can be seen that the present method is simpler, gives higher yield and involves less number of intermediates than the general method of preparation of 2-phenyl-5-aryl oxazoles starting from acetophenone^{2,3,7–18}. It also avoids the use of lachrymatory ω -bromoacetophenone and can be easily adapted for regular production.

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